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Spatio – Temporal Dynamics and Hotspot Prioritisation of Human – Elephant Interaction in a Transboundary Landscape: Evidence from Wayanad, Western Ghats

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Abstract

Objectives/Background: Human–elephant conflict (HEC) has intensified across the Wayanad landscape of the Western Ghats due to increasing land-use modification, habitat fragmentation, and recurring elephant movement through agricultural interfaces. This study aims to identify and prioritise conflict-prone areas using a structured hotspot ranking approach. **Method:** The present study assessed the spatial and temporal distribution of HEC hotspots across North Wayanad, South Wayanad, and Wayanad Wildlife Divisions using officially documented conflict records collected between 2020–21 to 2023–24. A total of 295 hotspots were identified and classified through a standardised frequency-based scoring framework integrated with Geographic Information System (GIS) analysis and Kernel Density Estimation. **Findings:** Among the identified hotspots, 134 locations were categorised as high priority, while 80, 53, and 28 locations were classified as medium, low, and rare categories respectively. The Wildlife Division alone accounted for 68 high-priority hotspots, demonstrating persistent elephant movement and repeated conflict near protected forest boundaries. A total of 7,155 human–elephant conflict (HEC) incidences were reported from the three forest divisions of Wayanad during the period 2020–21 to 2023–24. Considerable temporal and spatial variation were observed among the divisions. Spatial clustering was concentrated mainly along the eastern and southern forest–agriculture interfaces adjoining Bandipur, Mudumalai, and Nagarhole landscapes. Crop depredation remained the dominant form of conflict, while property damage and human casualties were spatially associated with recurring hotspot zones. **Novelty:** Unlike earlier descriptive studies in the region, the present work integrates hotspot ranking, spatial prioritisation, and temporal trend assessment into a unified management framework. The study provides a practical decision-support model for targeted mitigation planning, corridor-level management, and allocation of conservation resources in highly conflict-prone landscapes.

Keywords: Human–elephant interaction; Prioritisation; Conflict Hotspots; Management; Wayanad

1 Introduction

Human–elephant conflict has emerged as one of the most pressing conservation and socio-ecological challenges in tropical landscapes where wildlife habitats increasingly overlap with expanding human settlements and agricultural systems⁽¹⁾. Recent studies from South Asia have shown that habitat fragmentation, conversion of forest land, and disruption of movement corridors have significantly increased the frequency of elephant incursions into cultivated landscapes⁽²⁾. In India, the Western Ghats landscape represents one of the most ecologically significant yet conflict-prone regions for Asian elephants because of its extensive forest connectivity combined with intense anthropogenic pressure⁽³⁾.

The Wayanad plateau forms a crucial component of the Nilgiri Biosphere landscape and maintains ecological connectivity with Bandipur, Nagarhole, and Mudumalai protected areas and this transboundary linkage sustains key summer habitat of Asian elephants in the Brahmagiri-Nilgiri Eastern Ghats elephant landscape (Nilgiris), harbouring the largest breeding population in Asia with large-scale elephant movement across state boundaries⁽⁴⁾. However, agricultural expansion, infrastructure development, and settlement growth near forest fringes have increased the spatial overlap between elephants and human activities⁽⁵⁾. Consequently, crop depredation, property damage, and occasional human casualties have become recurrent features across the landscape⁽⁶⁾.

Recent investigations have highlighted that conflict events in Wayanad are not randomly distributed but are closely associated with land-use gradients, corridor bottlenecks, and forest–agriculture interfaces. The spatiotemporal clustering of negative human–elephant interactions in Wayanad demonstrated that human population density, proximity to protected areas, and temperature as major determinants influencing conflict occurrence, with seasonal hotspots concentrated in Kidanganad, Nulpuzha, and Pulpalli during dry months⁽¹⁾. Vineetha *et al.*, 2024 employed an Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)-based geospatial framework to assess elephant habitat suitability within Wayanad Wildlife Sanctuary and identified that highly suitable elephant habitats, particularly in Sultan Bathery and Kurichiat regions, strongly overlapped with zones experiencing elevated conflict intensity, indicating a close ecological relationship between habitat preference and HEC occurrence⁽⁷⁾. Studies also showed that conflicts intensified near forest fringes during crop fruiting and harvesting seasons, while delayed compensation and ineffective mitigation measures aggravated local livelihood losses and community distress⁽³⁾. Shajna *et al.*, 2025 studied the Human – Elephant Conflict in Wayanad through a quantitative landscape-level assessment integrating compensation analysis, spatial mapping of mitigation structures, and field verification surveys and observed that extensive crop loss, substantial financial burden, and multiple breach-prone areas contributing to the conflict intensity across the Wayanad landscape⁽⁶⁾. The historical forest-cover changes and landscape modification have intensified conflict vulnerability across key elephant habitats in Wayanad landscape⁽⁸⁾.

Spatial modelling and hotspot-based prioritisation will improve mitigation planning to tackle human – elephant conflict in forest mosaics⁽⁹⁾. Despite the availability of field-level conflict records, management interventions in many parts of the landscape continue to rely on reactive responses rather than predictive and spatially prioritised approaches. Most existing studies describe conflict occurrence patterns without converting them into operational tools capable of identifying intervention priority zones. Furthermore, comparative hotspot ranking across multiple administrative divisions remains limited in the Wayanad landscape.

The present study therefore aims to identify, classify, and prioritise human–elephant conflict hotspots across the Wayanad landscape using a standardised scoring framework integrated with GIS-based spatial analysis. The study further evaluates temporal conflict trends and examines the ecological drivers associated with recurring hotspot formation. By integrating hotspot severity assessment with spatial interpretation, the study intends to support evidence-based management planning and targeted mitigation strategies in one of the most sensitive elephant landscapes of the Western Ghats.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted across the Wayanad landscape of Kerala, India, covering North Wayanad Division, South Wayanad Division, and Wayanad Wildlife Division⁽¹⁰⁾. The landscape forms part of a larger transboundary conservation complex connected with Bandipur Tiger Reserve, Nagarhole National Park, and Mudumalai Tiger Reserve⁽⁶⁾. The study region comprises tropical moist deciduous forests, plantations, agricultural lands, and fragmented settlement zones that together create extensive forest–agriculture interfaces vulnerable to recurring elephant movement⁽⁵⁾. The climate of the region is predominantly governed by monsoonal patterns and can be divided into four distinct seasons. The southwest monsoon, occurring from June to September, accounts for the majority of the annual rainfall, followed by the northeast monsoon from October to November. This is succeeded by a cooler period extending from December to February and a warmer season from March to May. Annual

rainfall typically ranges between 1200 mm and 1700 mm, while daily temperatures fluctuate from approximately 19.8°C to 37°C⁽⁵⁾. Figure 1 shows the map of the Wayanad landscape with surrounding forest areas.

Fig 1. Map of the Wayanad landscape with surrounding forest areas

2.2 Data collection

Human–elephant conflict records from 2020–21 to 2023–24 was compiled from official field registers, compensation records, and incident documentation maintained by forest administrative units. The dataset included crop damage, property loss, human injury, and casualty incidents directly attributed to elephant activity. After removing duplicate entries and incomplete records, validated incidents were georeferenced using corresponding range-level location information. The final dataset consisted of 7155 verified conflict incidents distributed across the three administrative divisions. Where necessary, location details were standardised to enable spatial analysis. The dataset was further organised by year and division to facilitate temporal and comparative assessments.

2.3 Identification of HEC hotspots scoring and ranking

Conflict hotspots were identified based on the recurrence of elephant incursions recorded during the study period. Similar to frequency-based hotspot approaches used in previous HEC studies, recurring conflict locations were assigned severity scores according to the temporal frequency of incidents⁽¹¹⁾. Locations experiencing near-daily elephant incursions received a score of 4, weekly incidents were assigned 3, monthly incidents were assigned 2, and occasional events were assigned 1. Quarterly cumulative scores were calculated and subsequently used to classify hotspots into High (13–16), Medium (9–12), Low (5–8), and Rare (1–4) categories, thereby enabling prioritization of mitigation interventions.

2.4 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Spatial analysis was conducted using QGIS software. Kernel Density Estimation was employed to identify conflict concentration zones and spatial intensity gradients across the landscape⁽¹²⁾. KDE is a non-parametric spatial analysis technique that transforms discrete conflict locations into a continuous density surface, thereby highlighting areas of high conflict intensity or hotspots. The method effectively captures both the concentration and spatial diffusion of conflict incidents, enabling the

identification of priority areas for targeted mitigation and management interventions. Hotspot layers were interpreted in relation to forest boundaries, agricultural land-use patterns, settlement proximity, and known elephant movement corridors. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to compare hotspot distribution across divisions and assess temporal changes in conflict intensity.

To improve reproducibility and scientific consistency, the scoring framework was cross-validated with field observations from selected forest ranges and compared with hotspot characteristics identified in previous regional studies. The analytical workflow provides a transparent and replicable framework that can be adapted for conflict-risk assessment in other elephant landscapes.

3 Results & Discussion

3.1 Identification and Classification of Conflict Hotspots

The present analysis identified 295 conflict hotspots across the Wayanad landscape, confirming that human–elephant interactions are spatially concentrated rather than randomly distributed. Among these, 134 hotspots were classified as high priority, indicating persistent and severe elephant incursions into human-dominated landscapes. The Wayanad Wildlife Division recorded the highest number of hotspots (130), including 68 high-priority locations, demonstrating the strong influence of protected-area connectivity and transboundary elephant movement on conflict intensity.

South Wayanad Division reported 107 hotspots, with a substantial proportion falling into the high- and medium-priority categories, reflecting widespread conflict across this division due to agricultural expansion, habitat fragmentation, and proximity to forest edges. In contrast, North Wayanad showed comparatively lower intensity, with a greater proportion of low and rarely affected areas.

Table 1 shows the distribution of elephant conflict hotspots across three forest divisions in the Wayanad Landscape.

Table 1. The distribution of HEC locations across the forest divisions

Forest Divisions	High	Medium	Low	Rare	Total
North Wayanad	17	12	11	18	58
South Wayanad	49	26	23	9	107
Wildlife Division	68	42	19	1	130
Total	134	80	53	28	295

3.2 Spatial Distribution of Conflict Incidents

The study reveals a distinct spatial shift in conflict intensity across Wayanad during the study period. While Wayanad Wildlife Division emerged as the primary conflict hotspot during 2022–23, South Wayanad Division became the dominant conflict zone in 2023–24. It is observed that the eastern and southern portions of the landscape exhibited the highest concentration of conflict incidents. Major hotspot clusters occurred near Sulthan Bathery, Muthanga, Meppadi, and Kalpetta ranges where forest boundaries directly interface with cultivated land and settlement areas. These findings closely correspond with the observations of Morrison *et al.*, 2025⁽¹⁾, who reported concentrated human–elephant interaction zones along the Wayanad forest fringe. The present study, however, extends earlier work by integrating hotspot ranking and severity classification into a management-oriented prioritisation framework.

The concentration of conflict near ecological corridors and boundary regions supports recent findings by Shaffer *et al.*, 2025⁽¹³⁾ who emphasised that landscape connectivity and corridor bottlenecks significantly influence wildlife conflict distribution. Similarly, Fernando *et al.*, 2025⁽²⁾ highlighted the importance of transboundary elephant movement ecology in shaping recurring interaction zones across South Asian landscapes. The present results reinforce these observations by demonstrating that recurring hotspot formation in Wayanad is strongly linked to corridor continuity and agricultural expansion near movement routes. Similar relationships between corridor connectivity and conflict intensity have been documented across Asian elephant landscapes. Studies from Thailand⁽¹⁴⁾ and northern India⁽¹⁵⁾ have shown that fragmentation or narrowing of elephant corridors often redirects elephant movement through human-dominated areas, resulting in persistent conflict hotspots. The patterns observed in Wayanad therefore reflect broader regional processes in which landscape connectivity simultaneously supports elephant movement while increasing opportunities for human–elephant interactions.

Analysis of the most critical hotspots was done as characterized by multiple clusters within the highest conflict category in the various forest ranges in the landscape represented using a heatmap gradient ranging from green (low intensity) to red (high intensity), enabling clear identification of areas with severe elephant interactions in human-dominated landscapes. The Meppadi

Range, located in the southern part of the landscape, is identified as the most critical hotspot, characterized by multiple clusters within the highest conflict category (15–35 incidents), particularly along the forest–agriculture interface. This indicates frequent elephant incursions from adjoining forest habitats into cultivated and inhabited areas, likely driven by foraging requirements and movement along established migratory routes between the Gudallur Division of Tamilnadu and Wayanad. The adjacent Kalpetta Range exhibits moderate to high conflict intensity, with several localized patches approaching severe levels. These are due to fragmented land-use structures and the close spatial proximity of human settlements to forested areas.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of elephant conflict hotspots across three forest divisions in the Wayanad Landscape.

Fig 2. The distribution of elephant conflict hotspots in the study area

The Sulthan Bathery and Muthanga Ranges located in the east of the landscape form a contiguous high-conflict zone. Given their ecological connectivity with major protected landscapes such as Bandipur and Mudumalai, these areas experience frequent elephant movement across transboundary habitats, resulting in repeated interactions with human settlements. The intensity observed in Sulthan Bathery range is particularly pronounced, indicating a persistent and concentrated human–elephant interface. The Chethaleth and Kurichiat ranges display widespread conflict zones predominantly within the moderate to high category (6–15 incidents), suggesting key pressure points where traditional elephant corridors intersect with expanding human activities.

In the northern ranges of Begur and Tholpetty, conflict occurrences are more spatially dispersed and generally of lower intensity compared to the southern and eastern regions. However, the presence of consistent moderate-intensity zones indicates recurring disturbances, potentially linked to seasonal elephant movements through narrow forest corridors connecting the Brahmagiri and Nagarhole landscapes. The Peria and Mananthavady ranges exhibit relatively low to moderate conflict intensity. This pattern may be attributed to higher forest contiguity and comparatively lower levels of anthropogenic disturbance.

Overall, the spatial analysis indicates that human–elephant conflict is pervasive across the Wayanad landscape, with pronounced intensity in the southern and eastern regions. These areas are characterized by significant habitat fragmentation, agricultural expansion, and increasing human settlement overlap with traditional elephant movement pathways. Comparable spatial patterns have been reported from several elephant ranges across South and Southeast Asia. In Sri Lanka, Fernando *et al.* (2023) demonstrated that conflict is concentrated in landscapes where natural habitats directly interface with agriculture⁽¹⁶⁾. Similarly, studies from eastern and central India have shown that fragmented forest mosaics interspersed with settlements and croplands experience disproportionately high levels of conflict⁽¹⁷⁾. The concentration of hotspots in the southern and eastern parts of Wayanad therefore aligns with a broader pattern observed across elephant landscapes, where land-use change

and habitat fragmentation intensify human–elephant interactions. The observations highlight the need for targeted mitigation strategies, including the establishment of early warning systems, strengthening of conflict response mechanisms, and landscape-level planning to maintain functional connectivity of elephant corridors and reduce pressure on high-conflict hotspots.

Figure 3 shows the heat map of elephant conflict intensity across the Wayanad landscape.

Fig 3. Heat map of elephant conflict intensity across the Wayanad landscape

3.3 Types of the conflict

Crop depredation emerged as the dominant form of conflict throughout the study area, particularly in regions characterised by fragmented agricultural mosaics. High-energy food availability in cultivated fields likely attracts elephants into fringe settlements during crop maturation and harvesting seasons. Property damage and human casualties were comparatively fewer but remained spatially associated with repeated crop-raiding zones, indicating a progressive escalation in conflict severity within certain hotspot clusters.

Figure 4 shows the spatial distribution of different types of Human – Elephant conflict in the Wayanad landscape.

3.4 Temporal trends

A total of 7,155 human–elephant conflict (HEC) incidences were reported from the three forest divisions of Wayanad during the period 2020–21 to 2023–24. Considerable temporal and spatial variation were observed among the divisions (Figure 5). The annual number of conflict incidences increased from 1,293 cases in 2020–21 to 1,515 cases in 2021–22, representing a 17.2% increase. Conflict incidences further escalated to 2,315 cases in 2022–23, the highest recorded during the study period, before declining to 2,032 cases in 2023–24. Despite this decline, the incidence level in 2023–24 remained substantially higher than that observed during the initial years of the study. Although fluctuations may partly reflect improved reporting and response mechanisms, the persistence of high-priority hotspots across multiple years indicates that the ecological and anthropogenic drivers of conflict remain largely unchanged. Comparable increasing trends have also been documented by Goswami *et al.*, 2026⁽⁹⁾ and Naha *et al.*, 2026⁽¹⁸⁾ in other tropical forest mosaics where land-use change and corridor fragmentation intensified elephant movement through human settlements.

Figure 5 represents the temporal trends in Human – Elephant conflict in the Wayanad landscape.

Fig 4. Spatial distribution of different types of Human – Elephant conflict

The results indicate that human–elephant conflict in the Wayanad landscape is not randomly distributed but strongly structured along ecological and land-use gradients, particularly at the forest–agriculture interface⁽¹⁰⁾. The clear concentration of incidents along the eastern boundary and in areas adjoining contiguous forest complexes suggests that elephant movement patterns play a central role in shaping conflict dynamics⁽⁵⁾. These regions function as active interfaces where traditional ranging behaviour intersects with expanding human activities, leading to repeated interactions. The relatively low number of incidents within intact forest interiors further reinforces that conflict is primarily driven by edge effects rather than disturbances deep inside forest habitats⁽¹⁹⁾. This finding is consistent with recent studies that identify forest edges and ecotones as primary zones of conflict. In Sri Lanka, elephants frequently move between natural habitats and agricultural lands, with conflict largely concentrated along habitat boundaries⁽²⁾. Similar edge-driven conflict dynamics have been documented in India, where intact forest interiors generally support elephant movement with fewer interactions, whereas fragmented edges experience repeated crop-raiding events⁽¹⁵⁾. These comparisons suggest that the spatial structure of conflict observed in Wayanad reflects a widespread ecological pattern across elephant ranges.

The spatial overlap between crop depredation and areas reporting property damage and human casualties suggests a gradient of conflict intensity, with frequent foraging incursions potentially escalating into more severe forms of interaction. Seasonal peaks associated with fruiting and harvesting periods indicate that temporal availability of crops further amplifies these interactions, making conflict both spatially predictable and seasonally influenced.

The hotspot analysis provides important insights into the persistence and severity of conflict across the landscape. The high number of priority hotspots in the Wildlife Division, particularly in zones adjoining protected areas, suggests that conservation spaces are not isolated from conflict but are closely linked to surrounding human-dominated areas. This reflects the permeability of boundaries in a connected landscape, where elephant movement across administrative divisions and state borders contributes to recurring conflict. Similarly, the large number of hotspots in South Wayanad, including a significant proportion in the high and medium categories, indicates widespread and sustained interaction, possibly influenced by a combination of fragmented habitats, intensive agriculture, and proximity to settlements. Similar persistence of conflict hotspots has been observed in other

Note: Total represents the sum of incidences from South Wayanad, North Wayanad and Wayanad Wildlife Divisions.

Fig 5. Temporal variation in human-elephant conflict incidences reported in three Divisions of Wayanad during 2020–21 to 2023–24

landscapes where recurring elephant movement routes overlap with human land use. Studies from Thailand⁽¹⁴⁾ and India⁽²⁰⁾ indicate that hotspots often remain stable through time because elephants repeatedly use traditional movement pathways despite changes in land cover. The persistence of high-priority hotspots in Wayanad may therefore reflect long-standing ecological processes associated with elephant ranging behaviour and landscape connectivity.

At the range level, the emergence of specific areas, such as Mepadi, Sulthan Bathery, and Muthanga, as high-intensity zones underscore the importance of localised landscape features in shaping conflict patterns⁽¹⁾. These areas appear to coincide with movement pathways and corridor linkages, suggesting that disruptions or narrowing of these routes may concentrate elephant activity into limited spaces, thereby increasing the likelihood of encounters with humans. In contrast, regions with greater forest continuity and lower levels of human intrusion exhibit lower conflict intensity, indicating that habitat integrity mitigates conflict. Similar Patterns of high-intensity conflict zones have been reported in other transboundary elephant landscapes across South Asia where corridors intersect with expanding agricultural frontiers. Disruptions or constrictions in movement routes have been shown to concentrate elephant activity into smaller areas, thereby increasing conflict frequency⁽²⁰⁾. The ecological connectivity of Wayanad with the Bandipur–Mudumalai landscape likely contributes to a comparable process, reinforcing the importance of landscape-scale corridor management beyond administrative boundaries.

Temporal trends further support the region’s dynamic nature. The observed increase in incidents over the study period, followed by a slight decline, may reflect a combination of ecological pressures and management responses. While rising trends could be associated with increased interface between humans and elephants, the subsequent stabilisation may indicate the influence of ongoing mitigation efforts or changes in reporting practices. However, the persistence of high-priority hotspots across years suggests that underlying drivers of conflict remain largely unchanged and continue to operate in specific locations. Increasing or persistent trends in Human Elephant Conflict have also been documented elsewhere in India and Asia, largely attributed to habitat loss, agricultural expansion, and growing overlap between elephant habitats and human settlements⁽²¹⁾. Although annual fluctuations may occur due to climatic conditions or reporting efficiency, long-term persistence of hotspots is increasingly recognized as a characteristic feature of human–elephant conflict landscapes.

The persistence of HEC in several hotspot areas despite existing mitigation measures may indicate limitations in the long-term effectiveness of barriers and response mechanisms. Similar challenges have been reported in Northeast India, where the

effectiveness of electric fences depended strongly on sustained community participation and institutional support, with poorly maintained fences frequently failing to prevent elephant incursions⁽²²⁾. Such failures can create predictable crossing points that repeatedly attract elephant movement, thereby sustaining chronic conflict zones over time.

Compared with previous descriptive assessments conducted in Wayanad, the present study contributes a more structured and operationally relevant approach by integrating temporal trend analysis, hotspot ranking, and GIS-based spatial prioritisation into a unified framework. The findings therefore provide a practical basis for identifying high-risk management zones and allocating mitigation resources more efficiently across the landscape.

4 Conclusion

The study demonstrates that human–elephant conflict within the Wayanad landscape is highly structured across spatial and temporal scales and is strongly associated with forest–agriculture interfaces, corridor linkages, and fragmented land-use patterns. A total of 295 hotspots were identified across the study area, of which 134 locations belonged to the high-priority category. The Wayanad Wildlife Division alone accounted for more than half of the high-intensity hotspots, confirming the critical influence of transboundary elephant movement and ecological connectivity on conflict recurrence.

Spatial clustering was most pronounced in the southern and eastern sectors of the landscape, particularly near Sulthan Bathery, Muthanga, Meppadi, and Kalpetta ranges. Crop depredation remained the dominant conflict category, while property damage and human casualties were closely associated with recurring hotspot zones. Temporal analysis further revealed a substantial increase in reported incidents during the study period, indicating intensifying human–elephant interaction pressure across the landscape.

The major novelty of the present work lies in the development of a standardised hotspot-prioritisation framework that combines frequency-based conflict ranking with GIS-supported spatial analysis. Unlike earlier descriptive studies, the approach translates field-level incident records into operational management categories that can directly support decision-making and resource allocation.

The findings emphasise the urgent need for landscape-scale mitigation strategies focused on corridor protection, habitat connectivity, early-warning systems, rapid response mechanisms, and scientifically designed barrier interventions in high-risk zones. Future studies should incorporate movement ecology, remote-sensing-based land-use analysis, and predictive modelling approaches to improve long-term conflict forecasting and adaptive management. The framework developed through the present study can also serve as a replicable model for other elephant landscapes experiencing similar conservation and coexistence challenges.

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